

THE LINGUISTIC AND STYLISTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF ANALYZING MASS MEDIA TEXTS

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ANNOTATION

The use of language in mass media, for example, specific types of grammatical structure or specific intonation patterns, the content of the text and its cognitive meaning are of interest to linguistics. For example, newspaper headlines have specific syntactic features that determine their grammatical oddity and have long attracted the attention of linguists. It is unique in several studies that linguistic and stylistic analysis is carried out in ways that illuminate the socio-cultural analysis of news media.

Key words: *Linguistic and stylistic analysis, foregrounding, mass media, print media, news, broadcasting, discourse, article, political ideology, society.*

Introduction

Mainly, the analysis of media texts focuses on the correlation between the changing linguistic features and the changing aspects of the social context. While conversation analysis is primarily applied to informal language (e.g. telephone conversations), recent work has focused on institutional forms of discourse, including media discourse¹. For example, many studies have dealt with media interviews²

Methodology

Two forms of media in particular have played an important role in shaping the current understanding of mass media stylistics: the investigation of broadcast news (on radio and television) and the investigation of advertisements (usually in magazines or on television). Some features of the development of approaches to the analysis of each

¹ HERITAGE, John (1985): “Analysing news interviews: aspects of the production of talk for an overhearing audience”, in Teun Adrianus Van Dijk (ed.): *Discourse and Dialogue (Handbook of Discourse Analysis, vol. 3)*. London: Academic, pp. 95-119.

² HUTCHBY, Ian (1991): “The organization of talk on talk radio”, in Paddy Scannell (ed.): *Broadcast talk*. London: Sage, pp. 119-137.

of these types of discourse are presented below. Also, a third media format, media interviewing, is also doing a great deal of research and political studies, covering in-depth news and analysis articles; discussion formats, celebrity and chat show interviews.

Data collection and Analysis

Analysis of broadcast news became particularly important during the mass media era due to the social importance of the format. From the 1940s to the 1990s, there were usually a limited number of media channels due to limited broadcast spectrum, which created an atmosphere of influence and controversy around what was said on radio and television programs, and a barrier to public discourse: ownership controls, mandatory program standards, and a complex concept of balance that will be solved by regulation in the form of Following the growth of satellite, cable, and more recently Internet television, forms such as 24-hour news and individual news feeds, portable devices (such as smartphones)¹ have historically taken over from print media and radio challenged the dominance of broadcast news as the primary public source of information and opinion. In the main era of centralized, public broadcasting, radio and television news are still used in some settings. The news formats developed in television news evolved from earlier forms of radio news, propaganda films shown in theaters, and before that, print news. But the formats later developed in new directions. Television news has attracted particular interest in stylistics because of the political impact of its content and reception, as well as how its ever-evolving techniques contribute to the formation of political ideology.

Result and discussion

In print media, especially in the early period of stylistics, a particular area of study focused on newspaper discourse, including newspaper headlines. In the 18th and 19th centuries, "dramatic" stylistic changes took place in the register of newspapers, when newspaper prose became more like academic prose and saw an increasingly dense use of passive verbs and relative clauses². These changes focused on a more colloquial style, with changes to greater use of first and second pronouns, contractions, and idioms

¹ Kleineberg, K. K., & Boguná, M. (2014). Evolution of the digital society reveals balance between viral and mass media influence. *Physical Review X*, 4(3), 031046.

² Jones, B. D., & Wolfe, M. (2010). Public policy and the mass media. *Public policy and mass media: The interplay of mass communication and political decision making*, 17-43.

to broaden the appeal of newspapers. Through a corpus-based study, the specific role of compressed noun-phrase structures in the linguistic patterns that make up newspaper prose, especially headlines, has been revealed.

Through the analysis, we can see several elements that focus on different types of media discourse and provide an overview of new developments in mass communication studies from the point of view of critical discourse analysis. Media speech is the most widely heard speech, which includes news speech, advertising speech, television speech, film speech, colloquial speech, demonstration speech, etc. Stylistic linguistics became the critical analysis of speech, and cognitive linguistics became the analysis of speech text. With the innovations of printing and broadcasting, much of the first stylistic interest focused on transitivity. Transitivity essentially concerns who does what to whom, and is reflected in the structures of the arguments associated with these verbs: for example, when the subject of an active verb becomes an optional agent in the corresponding passive construction, it becomes the object of the active construction occupied by the various transitive models offer alternative ways of describing social activity in the field of conflict. Provides a basis for a critical approach to news texts.

Figure 1 Use of foregrounding in two types of media text: Print media and Broadcast media

The diagram above shows that despite the popularity of media broadcasts today, the public is less aware of foregrounding in broadcasts than foregrounding in media texts. We can see that print media has always had its influence. It is foregrounding that

highlights content in print media texts and prompts people to engage in cognitive analysis.

Conclusion

Cognitive analysis of media texts is one of the topical topics of the current period, through which the sphere of influence on the reader and listener is of primary importance. In this case, foregrounding increases the impact of conveying text content. We have observed to what extent the addressee is affected by the use of foregrounding types in modern media texts. And the extent of their use was shown in the percentage of correct use of foregrounding in public media broadcasting and media publication texts.

REFERENCES

1. Heritage, John (1985): "Analysing news interviews: aspects of the production of talk for an overhearing audience", in Teun Adrianus Van Dijk (ed.): *Discourse and Dialogue (Handbook of Discourse Analysis, vol. 3)*. London: Academic, pp. 95-119.
2. Hutchby, Ian (1991): "The organization of talk on talk radio", in Paddy Scannell (ed.): *Broadcast talk*.
3. Jones, B. D., & Wolfe, M. (2010). Public policy and the mass media. *Public policy and mass media: The interplay of mass communication and political decision making*, 17-43.
4. Kleineberg, K. K., & Boguná, M. (2014). Evolution of the digital society reveals balance between viral and mass media influence. *Physical Review X*, 4(3), 031046. London: Sage, pp. 119-137.
5. Mardh, Ingrid (1980): *Headlines: On the Grammar of English Front Page Headlines*. Lund: CWK Gleerup.